

Annex A.3.1 - High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin among certain *Salmonella* serovars

Annex to: EUSR on AMR in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food 2023/2024

High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin in *S. Kentucky*

Figure 1: Resistance levels among MDR *Salmonella* Kentucky isolates exhibiting high-level ciprofloxacin resistance from targeted food-producing animals, reported by MSs in 2023 - 2024

High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin among other *Salmonella* serovars

Figure 2: Number of *Salmonella* isolates displaying high-level ciprofloxacin resistance by serovar, reported from targeted food-producing animal populations by MSs in 2023 -2024

Annex A.3.2 Temporal trends in *Salmonella* serovars from poultry populations

a) Trends in resistance to Ampicillin, Cefotaxim, Ciprofloxacin and Tetracycline in *Salmonella* Infantis from broilers, 2014-2024

b) Trends in resistance to Ampicillin, Cefotaxim, Ciprofloxacin and Tetracycline in *Salmonella* Infantis from laying hens, 2014-2024

c)

Figure 3: Temporal trends in resistance to selected antimicrobials in *Salmonella* Infantis from boilers, laying hens, and fattening turkeys, all reporting countries, 2014-2024

a)

b) Trends in resistance to Ampicillin, Cefotaxim, Ciprofloxacin and Tetracycline in *Salmonella* Enteritidis from laying hens, 2014-2024

Figure 4: Temporal trends in resistance to selected antimicrobials in *Salmonella* Enteritidis from boilers and laying hens, all reporting countries, 2014-2024

Annex A.3.3 – Occurrence of antimicrobial resistance at the *Salmonella* serovar level

Complete susceptibility and multidrug resistance

The patterns of resistance associated with different serovars influenced the overall resistance levels in *Salmonella* isolates. In the main part of the report, the proportion of CS and MDR isolates among *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Derby*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Kentucky* from food-producing animals and humans are detailed. However, other serovars frequently recovered from each food-producing animal population also influence overall resistance levels in *Salmonella*. **Figure 5** and **Figure 6** show the proportions of isolates completely susceptible, resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes and MDR in *Salmonella* spp. and the most frequently recovered serovars from fattening pigs and calves in 2023, and broiler, laying hen and turkey flocks in 2024, respectively. Of note are the very high MDR levels observed in **S. Rissen** from pigs (50.7%, N = 142), **S. Newport** from broilers (61.8%, N = 36) and in **S. Bredeney** from turkeys (58.3%, N = 76).

(a)

(b)

N: Total number of isolates recovered; *monophasic *S. Typhimurium* includes antigenic formulas.

The MDR analysis of animal isolates included the following antimicrobials: ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin/amikacin, meropenem, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline/ tigecycline and trimethoprim.

Figure 5: Proportions of isolates completely susceptible (green), resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes (gold), and MDR (red) in *Salmonella* spp. and certain serovars recovered from (a) fattening pigs, and (b) calves, for all reporting countries, 2023

a)

(b)

(c)

N: Total number of isolates recovered; *monophasic *S. Typhimurium* includes antigenic formulas.

The MDR analysis of animal isolates included the following antimicrobials: ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin/amikacin, meropenem, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline/ tigecycline and trimethoprim.

Figure 6: Proportions of isolates completely susceptible (green), resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes (gold), and MDR (red) in *Salmonella* spp. and certain serovars recovered from (a) broilers, (b) laying hens, and (c) fattening turkeys for all reporting countries, 2024

Resistance profiles exhibited by particular serovars

S. Infantis was the most frequently recovered serovar from broilers (32.3%) in 2024 and the second and third most reported in laying hens (9.0%) and turkeys (7.0%), respectively. Although a wide range of MDR patterns were reported among *S. Infantis* isolates from poultry, the most frequent MDR pattern was CIP-NAL-SMX-TET, detected in 23.0% of MDR isolates from broilers, while for laying hens and turkeys, TGC-CIP-NAL-SMX-TET was the most frequently reported MDR profile (22.4% and 6.9%, respectively). Resistance to five antimicrobial classes was noted among isolates from all poultry origins, but was rare in laying hens and turkeys. Several *S. Infantis* isolates recovered from broilers showed MDR profiles AMP-CTX-CAZ-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 8) and AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 22). In *S. Infantis* recovered from laying hens and turkeys, only one isolate each was resistant to five AM classes (AMP-CTX-CAZ-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TET and CHL-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET, respectively).

S. Typhimurium was the second and third most frequently reported serovar from calves (17.5%) and pigs (9.8%), respectively. Among *S. Typhimurium* isolates, MDR was reported at a very high level in pigs (56.9%) and at a high level in cattle under one year of age (35.7%; [Annex A.2](#), tables 4 and 8). The most common MDR profiles in pigs were CHL-AMP-SMX-TET (n = 16), CHL-AMP-SMX-TET (n = 9), CHL-AMP-NAL-CIP-SMX-TET (n = 9) and CHL-AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 9). While two *S. Typhimurium* isolates from cattle under 1 year exhibited resistance to CHL-AMP-TGC-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET. *Salmonella* genomic island 1 (SGI1), known to contain a multidrug resistance region located on a complex class 1 integron designated In104, confers pentavalent resistance (i.e. ampicillin, chloramphenicol, streptomycin, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline resistance phenotype – AMP-CHL-STR-SMX-TET) and has been widely documented in a range of *Salmonella* serovars.

Monophasic S. Typhimurium was the main serovar recovered from pigs (28.9%), the fourth in calves (N = 6), the sixth in broilers (N = 38), and the seventh in turkeys (N = 22). Resistance to ampicillin, sulfamethoxazole, and tetracycline (AMP-SMX-TET) was the most frequent pattern in all food-producing animal populations, with 55.6% of MDR monophasic *S. Typhimurium* from pigs exhibiting it. The second leading pattern in pigs was resistance to CHL-AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 22). Monophasic *S. Typhimurium* has spread widely among European pig populations. The AMP-SMX-TET resistance pattern (together with resistance to streptomycin) is typical of the European clone (ST34) of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* (Hopkins et al., 2010). The genes conferring resistance to these antimicrobials are commonly found in association with IS26 mobile genetic elements, responsible for their integration at different chromosomal locations, as described in European strains of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* (Sun et al., 2020). It is noteworthy that multidrug resistance in the European clone of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* appears to have originated from the integration of MDR

plasmids into the chromosome, facilitated by the presence of these IS26 mobile genetic elements (Sun et al., 2020).

S. Derby was the second and third most common serovar recovered from pigs (28.3%, N = 418) and turkeys (12.0%, N = 82), respectively. In pigs, the most common resistance pattern in MDR *S. Derby* was AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 15). MDR with quinolone resistance (ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid) was reported in isolates from all animal populations from which MDR *S. Derby* was recovered, except calves. No *S. Derby* isolates exhibited combined resistance to quinolones and third-generation cephalosporins. Recent studies on *S. Derby* originating from the pork and poultry sectors in France identified four major host-specific lineages, corresponding to multilocus sequence typing (MLST) profiles ST39, ST40, ST71, and ST682 (Sévellec et al., 2018, 2020). The lineages ST39, ST40, and ST682 were associated with pork, and ST71 with poultry. While ST71 and ST682 isolates were generally devoid of resistance genes, ST40 isolates commonly harboured several resistance genes, with Clade 2 of this lineage characterised by SGI1 and the pattern of resistance to streptomycin, sulfonamides, and tetracycline. Additionally, a resistance gene for fosfomycin was detected in all genomes from ST39 (Sévellec et al., 2020). Moreover, *S. Derby* with ST40 from pigs, pork, wild boars and humans has also been reported in Spain with the most common phenotype conferred by the *tet(A)*, *aadA2* and *sul1* genes, located within identical or closely related variants of *Salmonella* Genomic Island 1 (SGI1; Vázquez et al., 2023). Two plasmid types (IncI1-Ia and pSC101-like), a class 1 integron, multiple insertion sequences and several intact or truncated transposons also shaped diverse resistance regions (Vazquez et al., 2023).

S. Rissen was the fourth most reported serovar from pigs in 2023 and exhibited high MDR levels (50.7%). The most frequent patterns found were CHL-AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 9, all by Romania except one isolate reported by Portugal), GEN-CHL-AMP-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 8, all reported by Spain), and AMP-TGC-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 8, all reported by Portugal). Indeed, most MDR *S. Rissen* originated from Portugal, Romania and Spain. In 2015 – 2017, an increase in the number of human clinical cases caused by MDR *S. Rissen* (ST469), mainly in the Azores archipelago, was observed, with most Portuguese isolates showing a high degree of genetic relatedness and a potential link to pork production (Silveira et al., 2019). Also in Spain, a major MDR *S. Rissen* clone has been circulating in humans and animals (García-Fierro et al., 2016). Moreover, *tet(X4)* has been identified for the first time in *S. Rissen* (ST469) from pork in China (Zhang et al., 2024). The authors found that the *tet(X4)* was located in the IncFIA(HI1)-IncHI1A-IncHI1B(R27) hybrid plasmid, and the structure of *tet(X4)* was *abh-tet(X4)*-ISCR2, suggesting an increasing transmission risk of the mobile tigecycline resistance gene *tet(X4)* beyond *E. coli* (Zhang et al., 2024).

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